

BLENDING FOOD AND YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

- A CONCEPTUAL STUDY

Sathish Vasudevan¹, Ashokkumar Palaniyandi²

ABSTRACT

In the recent past entrepreneurship has become a topic of discussion among youth. That too in India, startup India and Make in India has instilled a confidence among youth in the domain of entrepreneurship (blog.mygov.in, 2019). Entrepreneurship is the key driver of the country's economy. In developing countries like India entrepreneurship is one of the best ways for economic and social development. It not only creates wealth for the nation but also provide employment for a large population. Tough youth unemployment is a major threat to a country; in another way it is also a greatest asset. India being a county with more youth population, we have the greatest assets on one side and the unemployment on the other side. Hence to grow and stabilize the economy of our country, it is the need of the hour to develop the entrepreneurial skill of the youth. In spite of many entrepreneurial ventures available for the youth in our country, the scope for entrepreneurship in catering business is very high. The natural health food business in India was worth over 3.8 billion US Dollars in 2018 and there is prediction that it will reach over 8.5 Billion US dollars in 2023 (*Consumer Market Insights Food - India*, 2023). Global entrepreneurship Monitor survey affirmed that India has the biggest early stage entrepreneurship with 55%. The only way through which enough jobs can be created for such a huge populous, consistently, is by creating an environment for entrepreneurship and innovation. This paper tries to bring out catering and food business as an opportunity for youth entrepreneurs in India

Keywords: Youth Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship in catering, Food Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship in India

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Catering Science and Hotel Management, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore. sathish@psgcas.ac.in

² Associate Professor, Department of Catering Science and Hotel Management, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore. ashokkumar@psgcas.ac.in

INTRODUCTION

India has become an emerging market for global investors and the major contribution for countries economy is through entrepreneurship. Our country has taken many initiatives like Make in India, Digital India, Mudra Yojana, Atal Innovation Mission, 59 minute loan, Stand up India and Start-Up India which encourage aspiring and ambitious young Indians to become entrepreneurs. With the number of incubators increasing by 40% every year, startups in India is having a bright future (The Times of India, 2022). To promote entrepreneurship among the youth, the government of India has taken strategically planned initiatives Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendras have been converted to Entrepreneurship Hubs to facilitate entrepreneurship district wise which provides training and mentoring to interested candidates. Entrepreneurship both as a career option and economy developer has emerged as a strong tool to boost self confidence and economic empowerment. The emergence of entrepreneurs and small undertakings has successfully managed to take a toll on stagnant growth rates and rising unemployment rates. Because of its underlying benefits and advantages, many people especially youth is considering entrepreneurship as a viable career option where regular job opportunities fail to satisfy the needs and expectations of aspiring youth of both the developed and the developing societies (Shammi Agarwal, 2022). Taking entrepreneurship not only provides employment to the entrepreneurs themselves but also to others who get employed in their undertakings. It spreads the desire for achievement, independence and progress among individuals. It boosts creativity as entrepreneurs are likely to come up with ideas and opportunities that have not been traditionally explored and implemented. Of varying fields of opportunity there is a wide scope for food business among young entrepreneurs. This paper tries to explore food business and youth entrepreneurship.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this research article is to explore the potential of blending food and youth entrepreneurship in India. Specifically, this study aims to:

- Identify the key factors that influence youth entrepreneurship in the food sector in India.
- Examine the role of food entrepreneurship in promoting sustainable development.
- Investigate the challenges and opportunities faced by young entrepreneurs in the food sector.

This study seeks to contribute to the existing literature on youth entrepreneurship and food innovation by examining the potential of these two concepts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The pandemic has brought a great downfall for almost all the business and the most affected was the food business, the government across the globe has taken various measures to keep the pandemic under control (Apostolopoulos et al., 2021). All the measures taken have strongly influenced on the structure of demand as well as the entrepreneurial activity (Mastronardi et al., 2020). In the sectors like agriculture and food, entrepreneurship is considered as an important aspect which deals with challenges and the quick changes rising in the recent years (Gellynck et al., 2015) (MCELWEE, 2006). Youth entrepreneurship is not only supports the social and economical development, it is a vital determinant for future entrepreneurial activity (Abhishek Goel, 2006). Having a youth for every second person the scope for youth in entrepreneurship is wide , the opportunities for youth who have a educational background is very high (Ghazali, 1995)(Othman et al., 2006), it adds an additional advantage as they have acquired additional knowledge and skills , they will also have a good network building capacity. It is very much evident that entrepreneurship in food sector is a significant component for global economy (Moy et al., 2003). Few of the earlier studies these studies apparently shows that there is a good scope for food business among youth entrepreneurs

METHODOLOGY

This study is based on a conceptual model, and there are 20 research articles and few other resources verified. The suitable factors are identified to blend youth entrepreneurship with the food business. Insight information is provided to explain the opportunities, scope and challenges in food entrepreneurship. The guiding factors for food entrepreneurship like youth entrepreneurship, food market are discussed towards blending youth entrepreneurship and food business.

Figure 1 represents the factors associated with youth & Food entrepreneurship.

RESERCH FINDING

YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

The energy and the youthfulness of the youth in a country is the magical formula for quick progress of the country, in our country every second person is a youth and there is a estimate that India will be the youngest country n the world with more youth population (businessworld, 2022). The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor in its report 2020-2021 stated that there is an enormous opportunity for entrepreneurship in India, where 81% of the country's youth have the skill and knowledge to become entrepreneurs (ARJUN SHEKHAR, 2022). Youth entrepreneurship which is a source of job creation and social empowerment has got tremendous attention from the government, Industry and civil society organization. Ministry of skill development and entrepreneurship is the most significance evidence relating to youth entrepreneurship in India. One more survey by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) shows that entrepreneurship in India is having the highest innovation in whole Asia, 55% of total early stage entrepreneurial activity shows innovation among the new ventures.

FOOD MARKET IN INDIA

India, known for its diverse culture and vibrant colors, is also home to a vast and dynamic food market. The food market in India is not just about buying and selling, it is an experience that engages all the senses. The market is a reflection of the country's rich history, traditions, and culinary diversity. The food market in India is a bustling hub of activity. The markets are filled with all kinds of fresh and processed foods. The markets are not just limited to it, but also offer a wide range of street food, sweets, and snacks. The market can also be further divided into thirteen various segments like; Dairy Products & Eggs, Meat, Fish & Seafood, Vegetables, Fruits, Bread & Cereal Products, Oils & Fats, Spreads & Sweeteners, Sauces & Condiments, Convenience Food, Confectionery & Snacks, Baby Food and Pet Food. Revenue in the Food market amounts to US\$963.60bn in 2023. The market is expected to grow annually by 7.23% (CAGR 2023-2027). The market's largest segment is Bread & Cereal Products with a market volume of US\$173.90bn in 2023. In relation to total population figures, per person revenues of US\$678.70 are generated in 2023. In the Food market, 1.2% of total revenue will be generated through online sales by 2023. In the Food market, volume is expected to amount to 663,725.9mkg by 2027. The Food market is expected to show a volume growth of 6.0% in 2024. The average volume per person in the Food market is expected to amount to 419.25kg in 2023 (*Consumer Market Insights Food - India, 2023*). Another popular type of food market in India is the street food market. India is famous for its street food, which offers a wide variety of flavors and spices. The street food markets are found in almost every city and town in India. Some of the popular street foods include samosas, vada pav, chaat, and dosas. These markets are also a great place to try new and exotic dishes. The sweet markets in India are also a popular destination for food lovers. These markets offer a wide range of sweets, including traditional sweets such as laddoos and barfis, as well as modern ones like chocolates and cakes.

FOOD BUSINESS AND YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP

As the second populous country in the world India is having a huge market for food business. Entrepreneurship activities have been appreciated as a platform to add value to the economy (Estrada-Cruz et al., 2019). A variety of business from home based food to online foods and cloud kitchen is been done by the food entrepreneurs (Colpaart, 2017). Taking the unknown challenges, getting into risks and going an extra mile by pushing their limits are some of the

characteristics food entrepreneurs are recognized for (Knudson, 2004) and at the same time these entrepreneurs are very much significant for the economic development of the local food systems (McFadden, 2016). Frozen food in India is growing and in demand, from frozen momos, samosas to many the frozen food segment has captured the consumers need and market. The Indian frozen foods is projected to reach 306.61 billion by 2027 (Lisa Suwal, 2023). A pilot project on economic empowerment of women entrepreneurs and start ups by women (WEE) is implemented by MSDE, to enable an ecosystem through entrepreneurship education, Atal innovation mission which is started as a flagship event by NITI Aayog encourages entrepreneurship and innovation among youth across our country, this system works parallelly with central and state to promote an environment for growth of entrepreneurship and policies on innovation. Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana , ASPIRE and Start Up India are some of the initiatives by the government of India to foster youth entrepreneurship (Chetan Sharma, 2020).

OPPORTUNITIES AND SCOPE FOR FOOD ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

The food industry in India offers a wide range of opportunities for food entrepreneurs, and with the right combination of creativity, innovation, and business skills, entrepreneurs can tap into this exciting market. Each region of India has its own unique cuisine and flavors, offering a vast array of possibilities for food entrepreneurs. They can specialize in a particular regional cuisine and offer it through a restaurant or delivery service. Street food is a huge part of Indian food culture, and food entrepreneurs can take advantage of this by starting their own food cart or stall. With low start-up costs and a captive audience, street food is an excellent way for entrepreneurs to get started in the food industry. With the growing trend towards healthier eating, food entrepreneurs can explore opportunities in the health and wellness food segment. This can include offering healthy meal delivery services or starting a specialty store for organic or vegan foods. India is a major producer of agricultural products, and food entrepreneurs can explore opportunities in food processing and packaging. This can include developing new packaging technologies that extend the shelf life of perishable food products or developing value-added products from agricultural produce. Technology is transforming the food industry in India, and food entrepreneurs can explore opportunities in food technology. This can include developing food ordering apps, developing online marketplaces for buying and selling food products, or developing

new food processing techniques. With the rise in demand for catered events such as weddings, corporate events, and other special occasions, food entrepreneurs can start their own catering business, specializing in particular cuisines or dietary needs. India is a popular tourist destination, and food entrepreneurs can take advantage of this by offering food tours or culinary experiences that showcase local cuisine and culture.

CHALLENGES IN YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP

- The current youth are affected by the surrounding environment like family, teachers and society which in turn is not very much aware of entrepreneurship, and there are places where they do not encourage entrepreneurship
- Despite some recent development, the general argument is that there are not enough education and training programmes to promote entrepreneurship
- The lack of human, financial and social capital is a major barrier for today's youth
- Though there are many schemes available for financial support, obtaining an external fund / finance for a new business is still a Himalayan task for the youth
- Limited business network and business related social capital act as a consequences for starting a new business
- Another aspect which affect youth entrepreneurship is the market barriers

CONCLUSION

It is very much apparent that the youth are enthusiastic in starting a new business, and at the same time there are more number who do not want to take risk and have the fear of failure. As the youth entrepreneurship hugely benefits an economy by creating jobs, creating innovative products and increase competitiveness, more focus can be administered towards this sector. Fostering and developing an entrepreneurial mindset among the youth and equipping them with skills should be the primary preference. Developing entrepreneurial skills along with the infrastructure for entrepreneurship is mandate. Awareness on the scope of entrepreneurship from the school will provide clarity among the youth in this field. Though there are many sectors starting a food business has a huge scope, from street food carts to fine dining every aspect of food business has a good potential for revenue generation and entrepreneurial sustainability.

REFERENCES:

1. Abhishek Goel, N. V. (2006). ATTITUDES OF THE YOUTH TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP: A CROSS-CULTURAL COMPARISON OF INDIA AND CHINA. *Journal of Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability*, 3(1).
2. Apostolopoulos, N., Ratten, V., Petropoulos, D., Liargovas, P., & Anastasopoulou, E. (2021). Agri-food sector and entrepreneurship during the COVID-19 crisis: A systematic literature review and research agenda. *Strategic Change*, 30(2), 159–167. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsc.2400>
3. ARJUN SHEKHAR. (2022). *India needs more young entrepreneurs*. Idronline. <https://idronline.org/article/youth/india-needs-more-young-entrepreneurs/>
4. blog.mygov.in. (2019). *Youth Entrepreneurship: An emerging trend in India*. Blog.Mygov.In. <https://blog.mygov.in/youth-entrepreneurship-an-emerging-trend-in-india/>
5. businessworld. (2022). *A Nation Of Strong Youth*. Businessworld. <https://www.businessworld.in/article/A-Nation-Of-Strong-Youth/15-07-2022-437256/>
6. Chetan Sharma. (2020). *If You're A Young Entrepreneur, These Govt Schemes Will Help Your Startup Grow*. Youthkiawaaz. <https://www.youthkiawaaz.com/2020/11/some-youth-oriented-startup-schemes-launched-by-the-government-of-india/>
7. Colpaart, A. M. (2017). *Exploring Personal, Business, and Community Barriers and Opportunities for Food Entrepreneurs*. Colorado State University ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
8. *Consumer Market Insights Food - India*. (2023). Statista. <https://www.statista.com/outlook/cmo/food/india>
9. Estrada-Cruz, M., Verdú-Jover, A. J., Gómez-Gras, J. M., & Guaita Martinez, J. M. (2019). Entrepreneurial social identity and stakeholders: the socio-economic implications. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 14(1), 128–144. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-10-2019-0103>
10. Gellynck, X., Cárdenas, J., Pieniak, Z., & Verbeke, W. (2015). Association between Innovative Entrepreneurial Orientation, Absorptive Capacity, and Farm Business Performance. *Agribusiness*, 31(1), 91–106. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agr.21394>
11. Ghazali, A. . G. B. C. . & T. R. S. T. (1995). The determinants of self-employment choice among university graduates in Singapore. *International Journal of Management*, 12(26).
12. Knudson, W. . W. A. . C. J. . & P. H. C. (2004). Entrepreneurship and Innovation in the Agri-Food System. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 86(5), 1330–1336. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3697949>
13. Lisa Suwal, E. C. (2023). *Hot trends set to break more ice for India's frozen food industry in 2023*. *Economic Times*. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/cons-products/food/hot-trends-set-to-break-more-ice-for-indias-frozen-food-industry-in-2023/articleshow/97197179.cms>
14. Mastronardi, L., Cavallo, A., & Romagnoli, L. (2020). Diversified Farms Facing the Covid-19 Pandemic: First Signals from Italian Case Studies. *Sustainability*, 12(14), 5709. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145709>
15. MCELWEE, G. (2006). FARMERS AS ENTREPRENEURS: DEVELOPING COMPETITIVE SKILLS. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 11(03), 187–206. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1084946706000398>

16. McFadden, D. T. C. D. D. S. H. D. M. K. M. A. S. T. S. D. B. A. G. M. P. H. R. J. B. B. R. . T. D. (2016). *Economics of local food systems, The: a toolkit to guide community discussions, assessments and choices*. <https://hdl.handle.net/10217/226599>
17. Moy, J. W. H., Luk, V. W. M., & Wright, P. C. (2003). Perceptions of entrepreneurship as a career: views of young people in Hong Kong. *Equal Opportunities International*, 22(4), 16–40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02610150310787441>
18. Othman, M. N., Ghazali, E., & Sung, Y. (2006). Graduate versus non-graduate entrepreneurs in urban Malaysia: some insights into entrepreneurial personality, company and family background differences. *J. for International Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 3(1/2), 57. <https://doi.org/10.1504/JIBED.2006.011951>
19. Shammi Agarwal. (2022). *How the Emergence of Young Entrepreneurs is Reshaping the Notion of Youth in Biz*. Indianretailer. <https://www.indianretailer.com/article/retail-business/retail-trends/how-emergence-young-entrepreneurs-reshaping-notion-youth-biz>
20. The Times of India. (2022). *Number of startups in India grows to 72,993 in 2022 from 471 in 2016*. The Times of India. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/number-of-startups-in-india-grows-to-72993-in-2022-from-471-in-2016/articleshow/93077040.cms>